

FRANCESCA COPPOLA, CHIARA BENEDETTA BONI, SIMONA SAGONA,
VALTER DI CECCO, STEFANO TEMPESTI, ANNA MARTA LAZZERI
& ANTONIO FELICOLI

INTERSPECIFIC TROPHIC BREAKDOWN OF THE POLLEN
SOURCE BETWEEN WILD AND MANAGED BEES

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Bees play key roles in maintenance of ecosystems, providing fundamental ecological service and benefits thus representing an economic value for human society (GILL *et al.*, 2016). Flowering plant provide food to bees in the form of nectar and/or pollen. Nectar is a main energetic source for adult bees to meet energy needs to fly and a needful source for *Apis mellifera* for honey storage (WHITE, 1978; RODNEY & PURDY, 2020). Conversely, pollen source provides proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals necessary for brood rearing and development in both wild and managed bees as well as for young honey bees enabling their hypopharyngeal glands to produce jelly for feeding larvae (MULLER *et al.*, 2006; BRODSCHNEIDER & CRAILSHEIM, 2010; NICOLSON, 2015). Bees gathered from those pollen source that are available in large amount in the unit of time. A single wild honeybee colony will harvest 120 kg of nectar and 20 kg of pollen annually and these amounts can be greatly exceeded in managed colonies (NICOLSON, 2015).

Managed honey bees density and beekeeping are usually considered to have a negatively impact on wild bees populations (DECOURTYE *et al.*, 2019). Trophic competition between managed honeybees and wild bees is believed to be one of the main factors affecting different aspects of the wild bees biology, such as the foraging behaviour, reproduction, abundance and survival (GOULSON & SPARROW, 2009; HUDEWENZ & KLEIN, 2015; TORNÈ-NOGUERA *et al.*, 2016; LINDSTROM *et al.*, 2016; LÀZARO *et al.*, 2021). However, occurrence of interspecific trophic competition

between wild and managed bees has not been yet demonstrated and it is still strong debated (GORAS *et al.*, 2016; MALLINGER *et al.*, 2017). Pollinator-flower interactions are often quantified as flower visitation rates observed (LÁZARO *et al.*, 2021; DAPPORTO *et al.*, 2022). Wild and managed bees usually occupy different trophic niches and when overlapping occur the only observation of flower visitation by both wild bees and honey bees not necessary indicate competition.

In this scenario, the present study aimed to investigate pollen pasture utilization by wild and managed bees in different ecosystems at the same time. Palynological analysis of pollen grain gathered by both wild and managed bees were performed in order to assess which flowering plants sustain and provide feed for reproduction of bees populations. The investigation was performed in three Italian National Parks of Norther-Central Apennine and in three Islands of the Tuscan Archipelago National Park. Sampling was performed in early summer (June-July) and late summer (September-October) 2021. Taxonomic recognition of captured wild bees carrying pollen was also performed.

Palynological analysis showed a time-space breakdown of available pollen sources between honey bees and wild bees. In all the four Italian National Parks investigated, plant species used by honey bees as pollen source in early summer and late summer differ from those of wild bees. Pollen source sharing between honey bees and wild bees was recorded in early summer on *Rubus* f., *Trifolium pratense* gr., *Cistus*, Compositae S shape, *Delosperma* f. which pollen was gathered by different species of bumblebees (*Bombus terrestris*, *B. pascuorum* and *B. lapidarius*), by *Andrena decipiens*, by *Andrena cf. nanaeiformis*, *Lasioglossum albocinctu*, *Megachile parietina* and *B. terrestris*, by *Megachile parietina* and *B. terrestris*, by *Lasioglossum* sp. and *Halictus smaragdulus*, respectively. In this period of the year, these flowering species were abundantly present in the sampling areas. In late summer *Colletes hederae*, known to prefer *Hedera*, showed a marked preference for *Dittrichia viscosa* and little shared *Hedera* pollen with honey bees that only collected the latest.

Therefore, palynological analysis revealed to be an efficient quantitative method to study interspecific trophic partition between managed honey bees and wild bees populations. At the same time the main limit of this approach is the pollen identification at species level. For this reasons metabarcoding analysis on pollen samples collected in this investigation are in progress to achieve much more harvest pollen species identification for effectively quantify resource overlapping. The results obtained in this investigation indicate that a trophic partition between wild bees and managed honey bees occurred and pollen source sharing occurred only in period of high plant

species availability. Further investigation to clarify phenomena that led to the presence of this strongly pollen partition between wild and managed bees are necessary.

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Authors' Address — F. COPPOLA, C.B. BONI, S. SAGONA, A. FELICOLI, Department of Veterinary Sciences, University of Pisa, Viale delle Piagge, 2 – 56124 Pisa (I); email: francesca.coppola@vet.unipi.it; chiarabenedetta.boni3@gmail.com; antonio.felicioli@unipi.it; S. SAGONA, Department of Pharmacy, Pisa University, Via Bonanno, 6 – 56126 Pisa (I); email: simona.sagona@unipi.it; V. DI CECCO, Ente Parco Nazionale della Majella, Via Badia, 28 – 67039 Sulmona (I); valter.dicecco@parcomajella.it; S. TEMPESTI, Ente Parco Nazionale Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona e Campigna, Via Guido Brocchi, 7 – 52015 Prato Vecchio (I); stefano.tempesti@studio.unibo.it; A.M. LAZZERI, Ente Parco Nazionale Abruzzo, Lazio e Molise, Viale S. Lucia, 2 – 67032 Pescasseroli (I); annamarta88@gmail.com